
ABSTRACT

Recently, the domination vertex degree concept was defined in Chemical Graph Theory. In this paper, we introduce the first and second hyper Gourava domination indices and their corresponding polynomials of a graph. Furthermore, we compute these newly defined hyper Gourava domination indices and their corresponding polynomials for some standard graphs, book graphs, French windmill graphs and friendship graphs.

Keywords: *hyper Gourava domination indices, graph.*

Mathematics Subject Classification: 05C10, 05C69.

I. INTRODUCTION

The graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$, where $V(G)$ be the vertex set and $E(G)$ be the edge set. Let $d_G(u)$ be the degree of a vertex u . For undefined term and notation, we refer the books [1, 2].

Graph indices [3] have their applications in various disciplines of Science and Engineering. Recently some new graph indices were studied, for example, in [4, 5, 6, 7].

The first and second Gourava indices [8] of a graph G are defined as

$$GO_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [d_G(u) + d_G(v) + d_G(u)d_G(v)].$$

$$GO_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_G(u) + d_G(v))(d_G(u)d_G(v)).$$

Recently some Gourava indices were studied, for example, in [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

The domination degree $d_d(u)$ of a vertex u [16] in a graph G is defined as the number of minimal dominating sets of G which contains u .

The first and second Gourava domination indices [17] of a graph G are defined as

$$GOD_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v)].$$

$$GOD_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_d(u) + d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v)).$$

Recently, some domination indices were studied in [18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27].

We introduce the first and second hyper Gourava domination indices of a graph G and they are defined as

$$HGOD_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2.$$

$$HGOD_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_d(u) + d_d(v))^2 (d_d(u)d_d(v))^2.$$

Considering the first and second hyper Gourava domination indices, we define the first and second hyper Gourava domination polynomials of a graph G as

$$HGOD_1(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{[d_d(u)+d_d(v)+d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2}.$$

$$HGOD_2(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{(d_d(u)+d_d(v))^2(d_d(u)d_d(v))^2}.$$

Recently, some hyper graph indices were studied, for example, in [28, 29]. Also, some domination parameters were studied, for example, in [30, 31, 32, 33, 34].

In this paper, we compute the first and second hyper Gourava domination indices and their corresponding polynomials of some standard graphs, book graphs, French windmill graphs and friendship graphs.

II. RESULTS FOR SOME STANDARD GRAPHS

Proposition 1. If K_n is a complete graph with n vertices, then

$$(i) \quad HGOD_1(K_n) = \frac{9n(n-1)}{2}.$$

$$(ii) \quad HGOD_2(K_n) = 2n(n-1).$$

Proof: If K_n is a complete graph, then $d_d(u) = 1$.

From definition, we have

$$(i) \quad HGOD_1(K_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(K_n)} [d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2 \\ = \frac{n(n-1)}{2} [1+1+(1 \times 1)]^2 = \frac{9n(n-1)}{2}.$$

$$(ii) \quad HGOD_2(K_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(K_n)} [(d_d(u) + d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v))]^2 \\ = \frac{n(n-1)}{2} [(1+1)(1 \times 1)]^2 = \frac{4n(n-1)}{2} = 2n(n-1).$$

Proposition 2. If S_{n+1} is a star graph with $d_d(u) = 1$, then

$$(i) \quad HGOD_1(S_{n+1}) = 9n.$$

$$(ii) \quad HGOD_2(S_{n+1}) = 4n.$$

Proposition 3. If $S_{p+1, q+1}$ is a double star graph with $d_d(u) = 2$, then

- (i) $HGOD_1(S_{p+1,q+1}) = 64(p + q + 1).$
- (ii) $HGOD_2(S_{p+1,q+1}) = 256(p + q + 1).$

Proposition 4. Let $K_{m,n}$ be a complete bipartite graph with $2 \leq m \leq n$. Then

- (i) $HGOD_1(K_{m,n}) = mn(mn + 2m + 2n + 3)^2.$
- (ii) $HGOD_2(K_{m,n}) = mn(m + n + 2)^2(m + 1)(n + 1)^2.$

Proof: Let $G=K_{m,n}$, $m, n \geq 2$ with

$$d_d(u) = m + 1$$

$$= n + 1, \text{ for all } u \in V(G).$$

From definition, we have

$$(i) \quad HGOD_1(K_{m,n}) = \sum_{uv \in E(K_{m,n})} [d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2$$

$$= mn[m + 1 + n + 1 + (m + 1)(n + 1)]^2$$

$$= mn(mn + 2m + 2n + 3)^2.$$

$$(ii) \quad HGOD_2(K_{m,n}) = \sum_{uv \in E(K_{m,n})} [(d_d(u) + d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v))]^2$$

$$= mn[(m + 1 + n + 1)(m + 1)(n + 1)]^2$$

$$= mn(m + n + 2)^2(m + 1)^2(n + 1)^2.$$

In the following proposition, by using definition, we obtain the first and second hyper Gourava domination polynomials of $K_n, S_{n+1}, S_{p+1,q+1}$ and $K_{m,n}$.

Proposition 5. The first and second hyper Gourava domination polynomials of $K_n, S_{n+1}, S_{p+1,q+1}$ and $K_{m,n}$ are given by

- (i) $HGOD_1(K_n, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(K_n)} x^{[d_d(u)+d_d(v)+d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2}$
 $= \frac{n(n-1)}{2} x^{[1+(1 \times 1)]^2} = \frac{n(n-1)}{2} x^9.$
- (ii) $HGOD_1(S_{n+1}, x) = nx^4.$
- (iii) $HGOD_1(S_{p+1,q+1}, x) = (p + q + 1)x^{64}.$
- (iv) $HGOD_1(K_{m,n}, x) = mnx^{(mn+2m+2n+3)^2}.$

- (v) $HGOD_2(K_n, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(K_n)} x^{(d_d(u)+d_d(v))^2 (d_d(u)d_d(v))^2}$
 $= \frac{n(n-1)}{2} x^{(1+1)^2 (1 \times 1)^2} = \frac{n(n-1)}{2} x^4.$
- (vi) $HGOD_2(S_{n+1}, x) = nx^4.$
- (vii) $HGOD_2(S_{p+1,q+1}, x) = (p+q+1)x^{256}.$
- (viii) $HGOD_2(K_{m,n}, x) = mnx^{(m+n+2)^2(m+1)^2(n+1)^2}.$

III. RESULTS FOR B_n

The book graph $B_n, n \geq 3$, is a cartesian product of star S_{n+1} and path P_2 .

For $B_n, n \geq 3$, we have

$$d_d(u) = 3, \text{ if } u \text{ is the center vertex,}$$

$$= 2^{n-1} + 1, \text{ otherwise.}$$

Theorem 1. If $B_n, n \geq 3$, is a book graph, then

- (i) $HGOD_1(B_n) = 225 + 2n(7 + 4 \times 2^{n-1})^2 + n(2^{n-1} + 1)^2 (2^{n-1} + 3)^2.$
- (ii) $HGOD_2(B_n) = 2916 + 18n(2^{n-1} + 4)^2 (2^{n-1} + 1)^2 + 4n(2^{n-1} + 1)^6.$

Proof: In B_n , there are three types of edges as follow:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(B_n) \mid d_d(u)=d_d(v)=3\}, \quad |E_1| = 1.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(B_n) \mid d_d(u) = 3, d_d(v)= 2^{n-1} + 1\}, |E_2| = 2r.$$

$$E_3 = \{uv \in E(B_n) \mid d_d(u) = d_d(v)= 2^{n-1} + 1\}, \quad |E_3| = r.$$

(i) By definition, we have

$$HGOD_1(B_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(B_n)} [d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2$$

$$= 1[3 + 3 + (3 \times 3)]^2 + 2n[3 + (2^{n-1} + 1) + 3(2^{n-1} + 1)]^2$$

$$+ n[(2^{n-1} + 1) + (2^{n-1} + 1) + (2^{n-1} + 1)(2^{n-1} + 1)]^2$$

$$= 225 + 2n(7 + 4 \times 2^{n-1})^2 + n(2^{n-1} + 1)^2 (2^{n-1} + 3)^2.$$

(ii) By definition, we have

$$HGOD_2(B_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(B_n)} [(d_d(u) + d_d(v))d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2$$

$$= 1[(3 + 3)(3 \times 3)]^2 + 2n[(3 + (2^{n-1} + 1))3(2^{n-1} + 1)]^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +n\left[\left((2^{n-1}+1)+(2^{n-1}+1)\right)(2^{n-1}+1)(2^{n-1}+1)\right]^2 \\
 & = 2916 + 18n(2^{n-1}+4)^2(2^{n-1}+1)^2 + 4n(2^{n-1}+1)^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

By using definitions, we obtain the first and second hyper Gourava domination polynomials of B_n .

Theorem 2. The first and second hyper Gourava domination polynomials of B_n are given by

$$(i) \quad HGOD_1(B_n, x) = x^{225} + 2nx^{(7+4 \times 2^{n-1})^2} + nx^{(2^{n-1}+1)^2(2^{n-1}+3)^2}.$$

$$(ii) \quad HGOD_2(B_n, x) = x^{2916} + 2nx^{9(2^{n-1}+4)^2(2^{n-1}+1)^2} + nx^{4(2^{n-1}+1)^6}.$$

IV. RESULTS FOR GoK_p

Theorem 3. Let $H=GoK_p$, where G is a connected graph with n vertices and m edges; and K_p is a complete graph. Then

$$(i) \quad HGOD_1(H) = \frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np)(p+1)^{2(n-1)} \left[2 + (p+1)^{n-1} \right]^2.$$

$$(ii) \quad HGOD_2(H) = \frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np)4(p+1)^{6(n-1)}$$

Proof: If $H=GoK_p$, then $d_d(u) = (p+1)^{n-1}$. In K_p , there are $\frac{p(p-1)}{2}$ edges. Thus H has

$\frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np)$ edges. Thus

$$\begin{aligned}
 (i) \quad HGOD_1(H) &= \sum_{uv \in E(H)} \left[d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v) \right]^2 \\
 &= \frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np) \left[(p+1)^{n-1} + (p+1)^{n-1} + (p+1)^{n-1}(p+1)^{n-1} \right]^2 \\
 &= \frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np)(p+1)^{2(n-1)} \left[2 + (p+1)^{n-1} \right]^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (ii) \quad HGOD_2(H) &= \sum_{uv \in E(H)} \left[(d_d(u) + d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v)) \right]^2 \\
 &= \frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np) \left[(p+1)^{n-1} + (p+1)^{n-1} \right]^2 \left[(p+1)^{n-1}(p+1)^{n-1} \right]^2 \\
 &= \frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np)4(p+1)^{6(n-1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

In the following theorem, by using definitions, we obtain the first and second hyper Gourava domination polynomials of H .

Theorem 4. The first and second hyper Gourava domination polynomials of H are given by

$$(i) \quad HGOD_1(H, x) = \frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np)x^{(p+1)^{2(n-1)}[2+(p+1)^{n-1}]^2}.$$

$$(ii) \quad HGOD_2(H, x) = \frac{1}{2}(2m + np^2 + np)x^{4(p+1)^{6(n-1)}}.$$

V. RESULTS FOR FRENCH WINDMILL GRAPHS AND FRIENDSHIP GRAPHS

The French windmill graph F_n^m is the graph obtained by taking $m \geq 3$ copies of K_n , $n \geq 3$ with a vertex in common. The graph F_n^m is presented in Figure 1. The French windmill graph F_3^m is called a friendship graph.

Figure 1. French windmill graph F_n^m

Let F be a French windmill graph F_n^m . Then

$$d_d(u) = 1, \quad \text{if } u \text{ is in center}$$

$$= (n-1)^{m-1}, \quad \text{otherwise.}$$

Theorem 5. Let F be a French windmill graph F_n^m . Then

$$HGOD_1(F) = m(n-1)[1 + 2(n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2$$

$$+ [(mn(n-1)/2) - m(n-1)](n-1)^{2(m-1)}[2 + (n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2.$$

Proof: In F , there are two sets of edges. Let E_1 be the set of all edges which are incident with the center vertex and E_2 be the set of all edges of the complete graph. Then

$$HGOD_1(F) = \sum_{uv \in E(F)} [d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2$$

$$= \sum_{uv \in E_1(F)} [d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2 + \sum_{uv \in E_2(F)} [d_d(u) + d_d(v) + d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2$$

$$= m(n-1)[1 + (n-1)^{(m-1)} + 1(n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+[(mn(n-1)/2) - m(n-1)][(n-1)^{(m-1)} + (n-1)^{(m-1)} + (n-1)^{(m-1)}(n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2 \\
 &= m(n-1)[1 + 2(n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2 + [(mn(n-1)/2) - m(n-1)](n-1)^{2(m-1)} [2 + (n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 5.1. Let F_3^m be a friendship graph. Then

$$HGOD_1(F_3^m) = 2m(1 + 2^m)^2 + m2^{2(m-1)}(2 + 2^{m-1})^2.$$

In the following theorem, by using definitions, we obtain the first hyper Gourava domination polynomials of F_n^m and F_3^m .

Theorem 6. The first hyper Gourava domination polynomials of F_n^m and F_3^m are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(i) } HGOD_1(F_n^m, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(F_n^m)} x^{[d_d(u)+d_d(v)+d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2} \\
 &= m(n-1)x^{[1+2(n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2} + [(mn(n-1)/2) - m(n-1)]x^{(n-1)^{2(m-1)}[2+(n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2} \\
 \text{(ii) } HGOD_1(F_3^m, x) &= \sum_{uv \in E(F_3^m)} x^{[d_d(u)+d_d(v)+d_d(u)d_d(v)]^2} \\
 &= 2mx^{(1+2^m)^2} + mx^{2^{2(m-1)}(2+2^{m-1})^2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 7. Let F be a French windmill graph F_n^m . Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 HGOD_2(F) &= m(n-1)(n-1)^{2(m-1)} [1 + (n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2 \\
 &+ [(mn(n-1)/2) - m(n-1)]4(n-1)^{6(m-1)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: In F , there are two sets of edges. Let E_1 be the set of all edges which are incident with the center vertex and E_2 be the set of all edges of the complete graph. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 HGOD_2(F) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_d(u) + d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v))]^2 \\
 &= \sum_{uv \in E_1(F)} [(d_d(u) + d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v))]^2 + \sum_{uv \in E_2(F)} [(d_d(u) + d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v))]^2 \\
 &= m(n-1)[(1 + (n-1)^{(m-1)})1(n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2 \\
 &+ [(mn(n-1)/2) - m(n-1)][((n-1)^{m-1} + (n-1)^{m-1})((n-1)^{m-1}(n-1)^{m-1})]^2 \\
 &= m(n-1)(n-1)^{2(m-1)} [1 + (n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2 + [(mn(n-1)/2) - m(n-1)]4(n-1)^{6(m-1)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 7.1. Let F_3^m be a friendship graph. Then

$$HGOD_2(F_3^m) = 2m2^{2(m-1)}(1+2^{m-1})^2 + 4m2^{6(m-1)}.$$

In the following theorem, by using definitions, we obtain the second Gourava domination polynomials of F_n^m and F_3^m .

Theorem 8. The second Gourava domination polynomials of F_n^m and F_3^m are given by

$$(i) \quad HGOD_2(F_n^m, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(F_n^m)} x^{[(d_d(u)+d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v))]^2} \\ = m(n-1)x^{(n-1)^{2(m-1)}[1+(n-1)^{(m-1)}]^2} + [(mn(n-1)/2) - m(n-1)]x^{4(n-1)^{6(m-1)}}$$

$$(ii) \quad HGOD_2(F_3^m, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(F_3^m)} x^{[(d_d(u)+d_d(v))(d_d(u)d_d(v))]^2} \\ = 2mx^{2^{2(m-1)}(1+2^{m-1})^2} + mx^{4 \times 2^{6(m-1)}}.$$

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed the first and second hyper Gourava domination indices and their corresponding polynomials of a graph and have computed exact formulas for some standard graphs, book graphs, French windmill graphs and friendship graphs.

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